

Farm Ponds and the Rural Economy: Impacts on Cropping pattern, productivity, Income generation, and Challenges Faced by Farmers

Vikas Chaudhary, Prem Singh Shekhawat and Shivraj Kumawat

ISSN: 1542-2666

NAAS Rating (2025): 5.00

<https://www.jarvm.co/index.html>

jarvm.submit@gmail.com

2025; 20-1(Part-B): 75-84

Received: 10-08-2025

Accepted: 03-09-2025

Vikas Chaudhary

Ph.D 1st year scholar, National Dairy Research Institute, Karnal, Haryana 132001

Prem Singh Shekhawat

Assistant Professor, Sri Karan Narendra Agriculture University, Jobner, Rajasthan 303329

Shivraj Kumawat

Student of Ph.D second year Agricultural Economics, Sri Karan Narendra Agriculture University, Jobner, Rajasthan 303329

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17043406

Abstract

The study of the impact and constraints of farm ponds on cropping pattern, productivity, income, and employment in Jaipur district, Rajasthan. A sample of 80 farmers (40 farm pond beneficiaries and 40 non-beneficiaries) was selected from four villages using purposive and random sampling methods. Data for the agricultural year 2021–22 were collected through pre-structured interviews and analyzed using descriptive statistics and t-tests. Findings revealed a 42.90% increase in cropped area and a 29.47% rise in cropping intensity on the farm pond farms. Significant yield improvements were found, especially in wheat (24.69%), pea (23.74%), and groundnut (21.59%). Net income per household and per hectare of farm pond beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries by 73.76% and 35.96%, respectively. Employment generation increased by 108.70 man-days per household and 47.49 man-days per hectare annually. Constraints of farm pond farmers, such as high construction costs of farm pond, delay in payment of amount of sanctioned subsidy, and Complexity in documentation formalities constraints of non-farm pond farmers. The study highlights farm ponds as a viable tool for improving irrigation and rural livelihoods of farmers, while also emphasizing the need to address implementation challenges through policy and extension support.

Key words: farm pond, water use, cropping pattern, impact and employment

*Corresponding Author:

Vikas Chaudhary

Ph.D 1st year scholar, National Dairy Research Institute, Karnal, Haryana 132001

Introduction

It is true that India's progress depends on the expansion of the agricultural sector. One of the most significant sectors of the Indian economy is

agricultural. In India, approximately 55 per cent of total workforce was employed in agricultural and allied sector activities (Census 2011) and accounts

for about 18.80 per cent of India's GVA for the year 201-22 (Economic Survey, 2021-22).

In this context, India has looked to farm ponds as a means of realizing its possibility for agricultural development in rain-fed and semi-arid areas. Farm ponds are used to integrate planning regarding better utilization of land and water for agricultural production, taking into account both groundwater as well as surface water flow. Therefore, the cheapest source of natural water supply is rainfall. Its distribution is highly erratic and unpredictable. It becomes necessary to provide artificial water through irrigation in some situations and remove surplus water through drainage in others. Irrigation and drainage, or a combination of the two, makes up India's water management system. Farm ponds have a positive effect on employment prospects, high income levels and agricultural production. It supplies silt that is used in agricultural fields and that can also be used to fortify field embankments. Farm ponds aid in improving the soil's moisture content and also aid in the storage of extra rainwater and preventing flooding. Farm ponds serve as a vital supply of irrigation for summer time vegetable cropping in addition to being a source of additional income. Farm ponds are sizable tanks or reservoirs built to store water that is necessary for surface runoff. Farm ponds are mostly helpful for fish production, water supply for the cattle, plant irrigation and other tasks.

A farm pond is a large pit dug out in the earth, usually square or rectangular in shape, which harvests rainwater and stores it for future use. The pond is surrounded by a small bund, which prevents erosion on the banks of the pond. The size and depth depends on the amount of land available, the type of soil, farmer's water requirement and the cost of excavation and the possible uses of the excavated earth. Usually farm pond size has a range of $15 \times 15 \times 3$ meter, $20 \times 20 \times 3$ meter, $25 \times 25 \times 3$ meter and $30 \times 30 \times 3$ meter, respectively. Therefore, this paper has been made with aims to showed impact of farm pond on

cropping pattern, productivity, employment and income with that of non-farm pond farmers in the study area.

Research Methodology

Study Area and Sampling Design

This study was conducted in **Jaipur district** of Rajasthan, which was purposively selected as it ranks second in the state in terms of the number of farm ponds and is also situated in close proximity to the S.K.N. College of Agriculture, Jobner. Jaipur district comprises of four Assistant Director of Agriculture (Extension), Department of Agriculture, Government of Rajasthan, which is known as AD circles namely, Jhotwara, Sanganer, Shahpura, Jobner. Among them, Jhotwara AD circle is having maximum number of farm ponds. Among these, **Jhotwara AD circle** Jaipur district consists of 23 AAO circles (like Office of Assistant Agriculture Officer). Out of which, two AAO circles, namely, Jhotwara and Kalwar were selected purposively for the study on the basis of maximum number of farm ponds. From each selected AAO circle, two villages were selected on the basis of maximum number of farm ponds. Begas and Shyosingpura villages of Jhotwara AAO circle and Pachar and Lalpura villages of Kalwar AAO circle were selected for study.

A list of all farm pond farmers with the standard pond size of $20 \times 20 \times 3$ meters (i.e., beneficiaries) who received financial assistance from the Department of Agriculture, Government of Rajasthan, since 2020, along with nearby non-farm pond farmers (i.e., non-beneficiaries), was prepared separately with the help of Patwaris, Agriculture Supervisors, and other concerned village officials. From each list, 10 farmers with farm ponds (beneficiaries) and 10 farmers non-farm ponds (non-beneficiaries) were selected randomly. Ultimately, a total of 80 farmers 40 with farm ponds and 40 without farm ponds farmers were selected.

Primary Data Collection

Primary data were collected for the agricultural year 2021–22. The selected respondents were interviewed using a pre-structured interview schedule, specially designed to collect comprehensive data related to cropping patterns, productivity, income, and employment. Interviews were conducted at both the households and farm sites of the respondents to ensure accuracy and context-specific responses. Besides, the opinions on constraints associated with farm ponds and non-farm pond farmers were also asked to rank in constraints perceived by the respondents.

Tools and Techniques for Data Analysis

To evaluate the impact of farm ponds on cropping pattern, cropping intensity, productivity, income, and employment, both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were employed:

- **Tabular Analysis:** Used to compute percentages and averages for comparative evaluation.
- **t-Test:** Applied to assess the **statistical significance** of differences between beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers, using the following formula:

t-test

't' test was also employed to examine the impact between farm pond and non-farm pond as following formula:

$$t = \frac{|\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2|}{\sqrt{s^2 \left(\frac{1}{n_1} + \frac{1}{n_2} \right)}}$$

Where,

t= t-test

\bar{x}_1 = sample mean of the farm pond farmers

\bar{x}_2 = sample mean of the non-farm pond farmers

s^2 = combined variance

n_1 & n_2 = sample size of farm pond and non-farm pond farmers

Significance level on t-test at 5 per cent of probability

Cropping intensity

It refers to raising of a number of crops from the same field during one agricultural year. It was computed as follows;

Cropping Intensity = $\frac{\text{Gross Cropped Area}}{\text{Net Sown Area}} \times 100$

Garrets ranking technique

Garrets ranking technique was used to analyze the constraints perceived by the respondents of farm pond and non-farm pond farmers. The respondents were asked to rank the factors that limit in adoption of farm ponds. These orders of merit were transformed into units of scores by using the following formula:

$$\text{Per cent position} = \frac{100(R_{ij} - 0.50)}{N_j}$$

Where,

R_{ij} - rank given for the i^{th} factor by the j^{th} individual.

N_j - number of factor ranked by the j^{th} individual.

The per cent position converted into scores by referring to table given by Garrett and Woodworth (1969). Then for each factor the scores of the individual respondents were added together and divided by total number of respondents for whom score were added. These mean scores for all the factors were arranged in descending order and the most influencing factors were identified through the rank assigned.

Results and Discussion

In the absence of proper benchmark observations, the study adopted a comparative approach between farm pond beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers. This method assumes that both groups are subject to similar situational and

climatic conditions, thereby controlling for external influences. By ensuring that these contextual factors remain constant across the study period both groups, any significant differences in outcomes can be reasonably attributed to the presence or absence of farm ponds. Thus, to isolate and assess the impact of

farm ponds, a beneficiary vs. non-beneficiary comparison framework was employed.

Impact of farm ponds on cropping pattern

Land use pattern by sample farmers on farm pond farms and non- farm pond farms is shown in Table-1.1.

Table-1.1 Land use pattern by sample farmers on farm pond farms and non-farm pond farms during 2021-22 (In hectare)

Crops (1)	Average area on Farm pond farms (2)	Average area on Non-farm pond farms (3)	Average Change in area on farm pond farms (4)
Kharif crops			
Pearl millet	0.60 (17.05)*	0.52 (25.87)*	0.08 ⁺⁺ (13.33)**
Cluster bean	0.48 (13.63)	0.37 (18.31)	0.11 ⁺⁺ (22.91)
Groundnut	0.71 (20.19)	0.31 (15.42)	0.40 ⁺ (56.33)
Total of Kharif crops	1.79 (50.87)	1.20 (59.60)	0.59 (32.96)
Rabi crops			
Wheat	0.73 (20.76)	0.40 (19.90)	0.33 ⁺ (45.20)
Barley	0.49 (13.92)	0.25 (12.41)	0.24 ⁺ (48.97)
Mustard	0.16 (4.54)	0.11 (5.41)	0.05 ⁺⁺ (31.25)
Pea	0.11 (3.12)	0.01 (0.49)	0.1 ⁺ (90.90)
Total of Rabi crops	1.49 (42.34)	0.77 (38.21)	0.72 (48.32)
Zaid crops			
Onion	0.06 (1.70)	0.04 (1.90)	0.02 ⁺⁺ (33.33)
Tomato	0.11 (3.12)	0 (00)	0.11 ⁺ (100)
Chili	0.04 (1.13)	0 (00)	0.04 ⁺ (100)
Watermelon	0.02 (0.56)	0 (00)	0.02 ⁺⁺ (100)
Bitter gourd	0.01 (0.28)	0.007 (0.29)	0.003 ⁺⁺ (3.00)
Total of Zaid crops	0.24 (6.79)	0.047 (2.19)	0.19 (80.41)
Total cropped area	3.52 (100)	2.01 (100)	1.51 (42.90)

* Figures in parentheses are percentages of total cropped area in respective column (2) & (3).

** Figures in parentheses are percentages of change in area put under crop on farm pond farms over non-farm pond farms in column (4).

⁺ Significant on t-test at 5 per cent of probability

⁺⁺Non-significant

Table-1.1 The impact of study showed on farm pond farms, average of total area put under *kharif* crops was reported as 1.79 hectares which accounted for 50.87 percent of total cropped area. that the change in area put under all *kharif* crops was found to be increase (*i.e.*, positive) on farm pond farms as compared on non-farm ponds. Among various *kharif* crops, it was observed that change (*i.e.*, increase) in area under groundnut cultivation was estimated as maximum (*i.e.*, increase 56.33% area on farm pond farms over non-farm ponds farms) followed by cluster bean (22.91%) and pearl millet (13.33%). It was also noticed that, the impact of farm ponds on land utilization under all *kharif* crops was positive *i.e.* 0.59 hectares which accounts for 32.96 per cent of total area of *kharif* crops. The similar results of study were found by Jakhar *et al.* 2022. It could be concluded that, due to farm pond lifesaving irrigation, highest change was observed in the area of groundnut crop.

Under *rabi* crops, average area was calculated as 1.49 hectares *i.e.*, 42.34 per cent share in total cropped area in category of farm pond farms. Crop-wise, area recorded as 0.73, 0.49, 0.16, and 0.11 hectare under wheat, barley, mustard and pea cultivation, respectively. While, in category of non-farm pond, average area put under *rabi* crops was estimated as 0.77 hectares (*i.e.* 38.21% of total cropped area). Among the *rabi* crops, cultivated area was 0.40 hectare in wheat, 0.25 hectare in barley, 0.11 hectare in mustard and 0.01 hectare in pea.

It is evident from results of the study that an increase in area on farm pond farms over non-farm ponds farms was calculated at 0.72 hectare (*i.e.* 48.32% of total area of *rabi* crops) in case of wheat, 0.24 (*i.e.* 48.97%) in case of barley, 0.05 (*i.e.* 31.25%) in case of mustard and 0.10 (90.90%) in case of pea crop. Amongst these crops, both wheat and barley were found to be main crops which together accounted for 0.57 hectare change in total area under *rabi* crops (*i.e.* 0.72 hectare). It was found that impact of irrigation water with farm ponds on change in area under *rabi* crops had positive relationship.

In case of *zaid* crops, average area of *zaid* crops reported at 0.24 hectares which accounted for 6.79 per cent of total cropped area on farm pond farms. Among the *zaid* crops, area under cultivation of onion, tomato, chili, watermelon and bitter gourd was registered as 0.06, 0.11, 0.04, 0.02 and 0.01 hectare, respectively. While, non-farm pond farms, average area put under *zaid* crop was estimated at 0.047 (*i.e.* 2.19% of total cropped area). Among various vegetables, area under cultivation of onion and bitter gourd was found merely 0.04 and 0.007 hectare, respectively.

Cropping intensity on sample farms

The cropping intensity on farm pond farms and non-farm pond farms is given in table-2.2.

Table-2.2 Cropping intensity on farm pond farms and non-farm pond farms (2021-22) (In per cent)

Cropping intensity on farm pond farms	Cropping intensity on non-farm pond farms	Change in cropping intensity due to farm pond
190.27	160.80	29.47

Table-2.2 reveals that the overall cropping intensity was 190.27 per cent on farm pond farms and 160.80 per cent on non-farm pond farms. Thus, overall change in cropping intensity from non-farm pond to farm pond farms was 29.47 per cent. Although, cropping intensity due to adoption of farm pond was found to changed as compared to non-farm pond farms.

Impact of farm pond on productivity

Table-1.3 shows that average productivity of pearl millet was obtained at 1978.33 kgs per hectare on farm pond farms and 1892.36 kgs per hectare on non-farm pond farms. From cluster bean, productivity was estimated at 1505.46 kgs and 1440.67 kgs per hectare on farm pond and on non-farm pond farms, respectively. Thus, it was observed that, due to farm pond irrigation, productivity of pearl millet and cluster bean was merely increased as 4.34 and 4.30 per cent, respectively. This might be due to the fact that these crops like pearl millet and cluster bean in *kharif* season were comparatively more dependent on rainfall water in the study area but, there was given a supplementary irrigation through water of farm pond in case of lack of rainfall water. The average productivity of groundnut was recorded as 3166.16 kgs per hectare on farm ponds and 2482.56 kgs per hectare on non-farm pond farms. In case of groundnut, an increase in productivity registered as 21.59 per cent on farm pond farms. Similar result finding Thomas *et al.* (2009).

Table-1.3 Productivity of selected crops on farm pond farms and non-farm pond farms during the year 2021-22 (In kgs per hectare)

Crops	Average productivity on farm pond farms	Average productivity on non-farm pond farms	Change in the average productivity on farm pond farms over non-farm pond farms
Perl millet	1978.33	1892.36	85.87 (4.34)
Cluster bean	1505.46	1440.67	64.87 (4.30)
Groundnut	3166.16	2482.56	683.30 (21.59)
Wheat	3730.06	2808.92	921.14 (24.69)
Barley	3801.81	3041.62	760.19 (19.99)
Mustard	1162.44	985.00	177.44 (15.26)
Pea	9616.27	7333.33	2282.94 (23.74)
Onion	16187.50	15618.75	568.75 (3.51)
Bitter gourd	13867.60	11852.52	2015.08 (6.88)

In the study area, on the basis of the utilization of land under crops on sample farms (Table-1.3), all *kharif* and *rabi* crops were selected for comparison of average productivity of crops in both situation of farms *i.e.*, beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries. But, in case of *zaid* season, productivity of two vegetables *viz.*, onion and bitter gourd were only examined on farms of both categories. Because, amongst vegetables, onion and bitter gourd were grown on both farms like farm ponds and non-farm ponds. And, remaining vegetables like tomato, chili and watermelon crop was cultivated only in farm pond situation. So, these vegetables were not account for study of productivity. In case of wheat, an average productivity of wheat was estimated at 3730.06 kgs per hectare on farm pond farms and 2808.92 kg per hectare on non-farm pond farms. Thus, the average productivity of wheat on farm pond farms was increased by 921.14 kgs (*i.e.* 24.69%) as compared to non-farm pond farms. In barley cultivation, the average productivity was reported at 3801.81 kgs and 3041.62 kgs per hectare on farm pond farms and on non-farm pond farms, respectively. The overall increase in average productivity of barley was observed at 19.99 per cent on farm pond farms. Similar finding results as Sidram *et al.* (2020).

Figure-1.3 Productivity of selected crops on farm pond farms and non-farm pond farms

Impact of farm ponds on income and employment generation in the study area

This table reveals that net income per household per annum obtained by farm pond and non-farm pond farmers from different crops was ₹ 191419.91 and ₹ 50223.29, respectively. While, the net income per hectare per annum was estimated at ₹ 468973.42 on farm pond farms and ₹ 300325.28 on non-farm pond farms. It was observed that net income per household and per hectare was found to be higher (increase) which accounted for 73.76 per cent (*i.e.*, ₹ 141196.60) and 35.96 per cent (*i.e.* ₹ 168648.10), respectively, in category of farm pond farms than in category of non-farm pond farms due to increase in area along with shifting from rain-fed or less irrigated crops to more irrigated crops and enhance the productivity of crops through irrigation of pond water. Similar to Venu *et al.* (2015) and Dupdal (2023).

Table-1.4 Income and employment generated through farm pond and non-farm pond farmers

(Per annum)

Income/Employment	Particular	Farm pond farms	Non-farm pond farms	Change in income and employment	
1. Income	A	Net income/household (in ₹)	191419.91	50223.29	141196.60 (73.76)
	B	Net income/ha (in ₹)	468973.42	300325.28	168648.10 (35.96)
2. Employment	A	Employment/household (in mandays)	170.55	61.85	108.7 (63.73)
	B	Employment/ha (in mandays)	476.57	429.08	47.49 (9.36)

Figures in parentheses are percentages of change in net income and employment in respective row on farm pond farms.

Analysis of impact of farm ponds on generation of employment showed that per annum employment generated through different crops in farm pond situation was calculated at 170.55 man-days per household and 61.85 man-days per household in non-farm pond situation. It was indicated that, on farm

pond farms, increase in generation of employment per household was recorded as 63.73 percent (*i.e.*, 108.70 man-days) as compared to non-farm pond farms. In case of per annum per hectare, result find out similar as Reddy *et al.* (2020). Generation of employment was found 476.57 man-days and 429.08 man-days in category of farm pond and non-farm ponds, respectively. Thus, it was recorded that per annum per hectare employment generated was more *i.e.*, 47.49 man-days (9.36%) on farm pond farms over non-farm pond farms. There was also increase in area and productivity of crops resulted into generation of more man-days in duration of crop production in situation of farm ponds. These results contour with reported by Singh *et al.* (2017) and Jakhar *et al.* (2022).

Constraints associated with farm pond and non-farm pond farmers in study area

In both beneficiaries as well as non-beneficiaries of farm ponds, comparison of constraints associated with the sample farmers has been made ten constraints like high initial investment in construction of farm pond, lack of technical guidance of farm pond construction, high cost of skilled labour in slope and lining of pit-dig, lack of knowledge about life of plastic sheet, high expenditure on machinery labour (like JCB, tractor with trolley and leveler), problem in unearthing of deposited silt from pond, delay in payment of amount of sanctioned subsidy, depletion of ground water table, complexity in documentation formalities and subsidy amount released after the completion of farm pond, have been identified.

Table-1.5 Constraints associated with farm pond and non-farm pond farmers in study area

S. No.	Constraints	Farm pond farmers		Non-farm pond farmers	
		Garrett score	Rank	Garrett score	Rank
1.	High initial investment in construction of farm pond	65.53	I	66.15	I
2.	Delay in payment of amount of sanctioned subsidy	65.25	II	48.78	VI
3.	Subsidy amount released after the completion of farm pond	64.98	III	59.85	III
4.	High expenditure on machinery labour (like JCB, tractor with trolley and leveler)	64.95	IV	49.98	V
5.	High cost of skilled labour in slope and lining of pit-dig	50.55	V	48.30	VII
6.	Problem in unearthing of deposited silt from pond	47.30	VI	31.48	X
7.	Depletion of ground water table	47.03	VII	38.53	VIII
8.	Lack of knowledge about life of plastic sheet	46.43	VIII	33.40	IX
9.	Lack of technical guidance of farm pond construction	30.00	IX	58.30	IV
10.	Complexity in documentation formalities	18.00	X	65.25	II

The study identified several key constraints associated with the adoption and maintenance of farm ponds. Among farm pond farmers, the most pressing constraint was the high initial investment required for construction (Garrett score: 65.53, Rank I), followed closely by delays in subsidy disbursement (65.25, Rank II) and the release of subsidy only after completion of the pond (64.98, Rank III). Additional burdens included the high

cost of machinery and labor (64.95, Rank IV). There were reasons being that high rate of JCB machine per hours and unavailability at time, more expenses in lifting, spreading and leveling the dig soil on farm-fields. Similar finding was observed by Jakhar *et al.* (2022). and the cost of skilled labor for pit shaping and lining (50.55, Rank V).

For non-farm pond farmers, the high initial investment was also the primary problem (66.15, Rank I), but complex documentation procedures ranked second (65.25, Rank II), highlighting bureaucratic hurdles. Other major problem included the post-construction release of subsidies (59.85, Rank III), lack of technical guidance (58.30, Rank IV), and machinery-related costs (49.98, Rank V). Notably, lack of awareness about materials and issues like groundwater depletion and silt removal ranked lower for both groups.

Conclusions

The study found that the availability of irrigation water through farm ponds had a positively correlated impact on cropped area, cropping intensity, and productivity across all crop categories. The analysis revealed a clear increase in the total cropped area on farm pond farms compared to non-farm pond farms, primarily due to the consistent availability of irrigation water. This was particularly evident in the Zaid (summer) season, where a significant expansion of 80.41% in vegetable cultivation was recorded on farm pond farms, highlighting the role of pond irrigation in promoting off-season crop production. With respect to productivity, farm pond irrigation contributed to substantial yield improvements across several crops. The increase in average productivity on farm pond farms over non-farm pond farms was calculated as 4.34% in pearl millet, 4.30% in cluster bean, 21.59% in groundnut, 24.69% in wheat, 19.99% in barley, 15.26% in mustard, 23.74% in pea, 3.51% in onion, and 6.88% in bitter gourd. These productivity gains underscore the effectiveness of farm ponds in stabilizing and enhancing agricultural output, particularly for crops requiring multiple irrigations or those grown in critical climatic conditions.

The findings also demonstrate a significant economic impact of farm ponds. The net income per household per annum was ₹191,419.91 on farm pond farms, compared to ₹50,223.29 on non-

farm pond farms—an increase of 73.76% (₹141,196.60). Similarly, net income per hectare per annum rose by 35.96% (₹168,648.10) due to the increased cropping intensity and productivity facilitated by pond irrigation. Furthermore, the adoption of farm ponds was associated with a marked improvement in employment generation. The number of employment days per household increased by 108.70 man-days (63.73%), and employment per hectare rose by 47.49 man-days (9.36%) annually, as compared to non-farm pond farms.

Overall, these results clearly demonstrate that farm ponds significantly improve land utilization, crop yields, farm income, and rural employment, making them an effective intervention for sustainable agricultural development in semi-arid regions like Jaipur district. These findings underscore that while both groups face financial and procedural constraints, non-beneficiaries are more affected by systemic and informational barriers, whereas beneficiaries struggle more with implementation and operational costs.

References

1. Dupdal, Ravi, S.L. Patil, B.S. Naik, M.N. Ramesha and K.N. Ravi (2023). Farm ponds in northern dry zone of Karnataka, 59: 54-58.
2. Economic Survey of India. (2021–22). Ministry of Finance, Government of India. Retrieved from <https://www.indiabudget.gov.in>
3. Ghungarde, Dr. Dattatray Sheshrao (2021). Studied on impact of farm-ponds on changing cropping pattern: A case study of wadule village in parner tehsil of Ahmednagar district (Maharashtra), 38: 23-29.
4. Garrett, H. E., & Woodworth, R. S. (1969). *Statistics in Psychology and Education*. Bombay: Vakils, Feffer and Simons Pvt. Ltd.
5. Jakhar, Meenakshi, R.N. Sharma, Jitendra Kuri, Rakesh Natwadiya and Narendra Kumar Choudhary (2022). To measure the impact of farm ponds on beneficiary farmers

- in Jaipur district of Rajasthan. *Pharma Innovation Journal*, SP-11(2): 1583-1585.
6. Reddy, P.V.R.M., M. Girija Shankar, B. Janardhan Reddy, Y. Shankar Naik, Yerra Eswara Prasad and D.V.S.R.L. Rekha (2020). Farm Pond Impact Analysis of PMKSY-Watersheds Project in Srikakulam District of Andhra Pradesh. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.*, 9(12): 1719-1729.
 7. Sidram, B., S. Kammar, D. Biraladinni and R.M. Sambrani (2020). A study on utilization pattern of farm ponds constructed by the farmers in Kalyana Karnataka region of Karnataka state. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.*, 9(11): 2614-2621.
 8. Singh, H., S.S. Burark, S.K. Sharma, D.K. Jajoria and R.P. Sharma (2017). Economic evaluation of farming systems for agricultural production in Southern Rajasthan. *Economic Affairs*, 62(1): 47-53
 9. Thomas, K. Jesy, K. Satheesh Babu and E.K. Thomas (2009). Watershed-based development for rural prosperity-evidences from Kerala. *Agricultural Economics Research Review*, 22: 407-414.
 10. Venu, B.N, Ravi Simha L. and V. Venkataramana Reddy (2015). Economic analysis of farm ponds in tungabhadra project command area of karanataka.